

EFFECT OF GAME-SPECIFIC TRAINING ON SELECTED PERFORMANCE VARIABLES AMONG INTER-COLLEGIATE MALE HOCKEY PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of game-specific training on selected performance variables among inter-collegiate male hockey players. It was hypothesized that there would be significant differences on selected performance variables due to the effect of among inter-collegiate male hockey players. For the present study the 36 male intercollegiate level players were selected as subjects at random from affiliated colleges of Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli, Tamilnadu, India and their ages ranged from 18 to 25 years. For the present study pre test – post test random group design which consists of control group and experimental group was used.

The subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups of eighteen each and named as Group 'A' and Group 'B'. Group 'A' underwent game-specific training and Group 'B' has not undergone any training. Performance variables were assessed by using Suresh & Kalidasan skill test battery (2010). True randomized experimental group design has been employed with two groups, namely game-specific training group and control group with 15 subjects each. Experimental group underwent the treatments for a period of twelve weeks and no training was given to the control group. The two groups were statistically analysed by using dependent 't' test. The result of the study reveals that there was a significant improvement in the game-specific training group on selected variables when compared to the control group after the completion of twelve weeks of game-specific training.

Key Words: Dribbling, Hit, Hockey

Introduction:

The history of hockey traced to ancient and modern was presented here. In addition to this to have its development and its present status, the worldwide-standardized tournament with its structure such as world cup, Asia cup and champions trophy. The game of hockey loses its fame in the international competition. In first four decades of Olympic and world cup of hockey Indian maintain its position in No.1. But in the last four decades, the performance of Indian hockey at Olympics and world cup is a dismal show except 1980 Olympics. Besides, the very sorry state of affairs observed in the performance of Indian hockey is they have to play qualifying round ever for participation at the standard tournaments of above said.

The reasons for having such dismal show as pointed out by former Indian hockey players, journalists, public and most fervent of hockey are narrow state of population. As for as participants concerned, they are lagging in physical and psychological aspects needed for high level competition. Of these, the present study mainly focused on analyzing the psychological aspects of players very specifically on their positions. Earlier studies have already been confirmed that players of different sports are differed on psychological aspects. Based on this, the present study has been focused to identify the perception towards the competition of players of various positions in hockey (Dureha & Akhil, 2003).

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of game-specific training on selected performance variables among inter-collegiate male hockey players. It was hypothesized that there would be significant differences on selected performance variables due to the effect of among inter-collegiate male hockey players. For the present study the 36 male intercollegiate level players were selected as subjects at random from affiliated colleges of Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli, Tamilnadu, India and their ages ranged from 18 to 25 years. For the present study pre test – post test random group design which consists of control group and experimental group was used. The subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups of eighteen each and named as Group 'A' and Group 'B'. Group 'A' underwent game-specific training and Group 'B' has not undergone any training.

Results and Discussion:

The detailed procedure of analysis of data and interpretation were given below,

Table 1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics on Performance Variables among Inter-Collegiate Male Hockey Players

S.No	Variables	GSTG					CG				
		Pre	SD (±)	Post	SD (±)	AM	Pre	SD (±)	Post	SD (±)	AM
1	Speed Dribbling	7.66	0.31	5.92	0.57	5.92	7.59	0.35	7.38	0.34	7.38
2	Slap Hit	12.77	3.07	19.72	2.69	19.61	12.22	3.07	12.77	3.91	12.88

GSTG = Game-specific training Group

CG = Control Group

The table I shows that the pre and post test means and standard deviation of two groups on performance variables of inter-collegiate male hockey players.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance of Pre Test Scores on Performance Variables among Inter-Collegiate Male Hockey Players

S.No	Variables	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F-Value
1	Speed Dribbling	BG	0.04	1	0.04	0.40
		WG	3.80	34	0.11	
2	Slap Hit	BG	2.77	1	2.77	0.29
		WG	322.22	34	9.47	

* P < 0.05 Table F, df (1,28) (0.05) = 4.19

In table 2, the results of analysis of variance of pre test scores on Speed Dribbling (0.40) and slap hit (0.29) were lesser than the table value of 4.13 indicating that it was not significant for the degrees of freedom (1,34) at 0.05 level of confidence indicating that the random sampling was successful.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance of Post Test Scores on Performance Variables among Inter-Collegiate Male Hockey Players

S.No	Variables	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F-Value
1	Speed Dribbling	BG	19.01	1	19.01	84.71*
		WG	7.62	34	0.22	
2	Slap Hit	BG	434.02	1	434.02	38.35*
		WG	384.72	34	11.31	

* P < 0.05 Table F, df (1,28) (0.05) = 4.19

In table 3, the results of analysis of variance of post test scores on Speed Dribbling (84.71) & slap hit (38.35) were greater than the table value of 4.13 indicating that it was not significant for the degrees of freedom (1,34) at 0.05 level of confidence.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance of Adjusted Post Test Scores on Performance Variables among Inter-Collegiate Male Hockey Players

S.No	Variables	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F-Value
1	Speed Dribbling	BG	18.77	1	18.77	81.22*
		WG	7.62	33	0.23	
2	Slap Hit	BG	403.44	1	403.44	39.85*
		WG	334.05	33	10.12	

* P < 0.05 Table F, df (1,27) (0.05) = 4.21

In table 4, the results of analysis of covariance of adjusted post test scores Speed Dribbling (183.24) and slap hit (141.06) were greater than the table value of 4.13 indicating that it was not significant for the degrees of freedom (1,33) at 0.05 level of confidence.

Conclusion:

The result of the study reveals that there was a significant improvement in the game-specific training group on selected variables when compared to the control group after the completion of twelve weeks of game-specific training.

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